

Comparison of a novel wearable electronic UV dosimeter with reference instrumentation and first on-field deployment for personal exposure assessment

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Abstract

Monitoring solar ultraviolet (UV) radiation is of paramount importance to assess its impacts on human health. Environmental solar UV irradiance is typically measured using radiometers with reference to a fixed horizontal surface, which may not accurately represent human body exposure. To address this issue, various types of personal dosimeters have been developed to better characterize individual exposure. In this study, the performances of a recently designed wearable electronic dosimeter (EUV) developed by M. Allen at the University of Canterbury, Christchurch, New Zealand are evaluated. To our knowledge, it is the first time that this specific type of dosimeter is tested in Italy. Initially, three dosimeters are compared with a co-located broadband radiometer (SUV-E) and a double-monochromator spectroradiometer (Bentham DTMc300F) physically traceable to the SI unit system operated at the solar and atmospheric observatory of Aosta–Saint-Christophe (Italy, 570 m a.s.l.), headquarter of the Environmental Protection Agency (ARPA) of the Aosta Valley, on the floor of an Alpine valley. The dosimeters are exposed to the sun in the horizontal orientation. It is demonstrated that the dosimeters can be easily calibrated to provide the global solar UV index within 10% accuracy to the reference radiometer after calibration and with 10% discrepancy among each dosimeter (precision) after calibration. Subsequently, the dosimeters are employed to assess the personal exposure of two individuals in their day-to-day life on the valley floor (550-700 m a.s.l.) and that of another individual hiking at high altitudes (1700-2400 m a.s.l.). It is found that UV exposure of the former group is very low even in summer (which can ultimately lead to vitamin D deficiency), while prolonged exposure at high altitudes can easily cause erythema even after a single application of a UV sunscreen. The results of instrumental tests which followed the campaigns highlight the importance of carefully checking the stability of the dosimeters each time after employing them in the field. The data presented in this study showcase the use of a device capable of characterizing human exposure to solar UV radiation.

1. Introduction

The spectrum of the solar radiation detected at the Earth's surface extends over three wavelength ranges: ultraviolet (UV), visible and near infrared (IR). UV radiation (UVR) has a higher frequency (lower wavelength) than visible light. It is conventionally separated in three spectral bands: UV-A (315-400 nm), UV-B (280-315 nm) and UV-C (<280 nm). The first two are the main ranges of wavelengths that are commonly measured at the Earth's surface, whereas radiation in the last band, far more ionizing and detrimental, is completely absorbed by oxygen and ozone in the upper atmosphere. UV-B is massively absorbed by the ozone in the stratosphere, however a small amount of UV-B radiation (about 5 % of total UVR) reaches the surface. Hence, most of the UVR living organisms are exposed to, at the Earth's surface, is from the UV-A band.

It is important to constantly monitor the amount of UVR reaching the surface, since it has many direct and indirect effects on life. For example, UVR impacts tropospheric chemistry, as it drives photochemical reactions leading to the production of secondary pollutants (photochemical smog). Most importantly, UV-A and UV-B radiation is also known to cause multiple significant biological responses on the Earth's flora and fauna, including humans (Zerefos et al., 2023). The impacts can be both positive and negative. In fact, UVR is responsible for the production of vitamin D in humans and most vertebrates, thus playing a significant role in their metabolism and calcium homeostasis. The benefits of vitamin D on musculoskeletal health are established, while other health benefits are controversial (Lucas et al., 2019). However, UVR is also commonly considered harmful because it can cause various health issues in case of high exposure, including severe sunburn, skin irritation, eye diseases and, in the long term, premature aging and skin cancer.

These effects have stimulated researchers to measure human exposure to UVR, i.e. the amount of energy reaching an area of the body over a period of time. Since the 1970s, UVR received by individuals has been assessed with many different methods. The first dosimeters (the name of which is derived from the fact that they measure the UV personal "dose", i.e. the radiant exposure to sunlight) were polysulfone films that darken as a function of the amount of UVR that they receive (e.g., Siani et al., 2008; Diffey, 2020). Technology has progressed over the last few years and scientists have developed miniaturized detectors capable of quantifying the UV personal exposure, e.g. electronic dosimeters.

This study is aimed at testing the accuracy of a new type of wearable electronic UV dosimeters (EUV, Sect. 2), developed by Assoc. Prof. Martin Allen at the University of Canterbury, Christchurch, New Zealand (Allen et al., 2020). First, the dosimeter performances were evaluated (Sect. 3.1-3.3) by comparing their output to reference instrumentation, physically traceable to the SI unit system, at the solar and atmospheric observatory of the Environmental Protection Agency (ARPA) of the Aosta Valley, Italy (Fountoulakis et al., 2020). This also allowed us to fine-tune the calibration coefficients provided by the manufacturer. Subsequently (Sect. 3.4), the dosimeters were employed for a personal dosimetry campaign involving a few volunteers. The issues encountered during the use of EUVs are discussed in Sect. 4. Conclusions are drawn in Sect. 5.

Table 1: Equivalence between skin types and Minimum Erythemal Dose (MED).

Skin type	Tan	Burn	Hair colour	Eye colour	1 MED
I	never	always	red	blue	200 J·m ⁻²
II	sometimes	sometimes	blond	blue/green	250 J·m ⁻²
III	always	rarely	brown	gray/brown	350 J·m ⁻²
IV	always	never	black	brown	450 J·m ⁻²

2. Data and Methods

2.1 Definition of the physical quantities employed in the study

The erythemally weighted radiant exposure (“dose”, in short) can be used to express the erythemal potential of UVR. It is calculated by weighting the solar spectrum with the erythemal action spectrum as defined by Commission Internationale de l’Eclairage (CIE; ISO/CIE 2019) and by integrating the result over wavelength and exposure time. The Minimum Erythemal Dose (MED) can thus be defined as the least amount of UVR triggering a noticeable reddening of previously unexposed skin, which is about 200 J m⁻² of erythemally-weighted UV in fair skinned individuals. The actual amount of UVR depends on the skin pigmentation of the individual (Fitzpatrick, 1988). Four skin types were defined and the equivalent of 1 MED for each one was determined (Table 1, CIE 2014). Taking into consideration the European population, the phototypes include the most sensitive individuals belonging to the first skin type (often with blue eyes and red hair, 1 MED might be around 200 J m⁻²), up to the least sensitive ones in the fourth group (e.g., with black hair and brown eyes, 1 MED being around 450 J m⁻²).

Differently from the MED, which refers to personal exposure, the UV Index (UVI) is used to quantify the level of potentially harmful UV radiation to the public. However, this variable is defined with reference to a horizontal surface (environmental radiation). The UVI is obtained by weighting the UV solar irradiance spectrum at the Earth’s surface (UV-B and UV-A) with the erythemal spectrum and then multiplying the result by 40 m² W⁻¹ (COST-713, 2000). This scaling factor is defined so that the UVI reaches values between 8 and 10 at mid-latitudes in summer.

2.2 Instruments

Initially developed in 2005 at the University of Canterbury, Christchurch, New Zealand, the EUV dosimeter works by amplifying a small photocurrent produced by an aluminum gallium nitride (AlGaN) Schottky photodiode when illuminated with UVR. This signal (which will be referred to as “raw counts” from now on) is then internally converted into a UVI output by multiplying the signal by a calibration factor after subtraction of a dark signal. The instrument

Figure 1: One of the EUVs employed in the study.

(Fig. 1) has a UV-transparent quartz window and is covered by polytetrafluoroethylene (PTFE) diffuser to obtain a broader angular response and simulate the cosine response of flat surfaces, such as the human skin. EUVs can be programmed by the user to record UVR every 2 to 120 s, but for most studies they are set to record every 8 s. The recorded irradiance can be integrated over time to have the UVR dose. The counts and UVI are stored in memory, which can keep up to 131,000 readings. Data is transferred through a 3-pin miniature port to USB-A cable that can be plugged into any computer. Calibration factors are saved as metadata. The specific instruments that were employed in this study (serial numbers SU01, SU02 and SU09) are part of a larger batch recently acquired by Sapienza - University of Rome.

The reference instruments here employed to determine the UV Index are broadband UV radiometers (Kipp&Zonen, SUV-E) operated at the solar and atmospheric observatory of ARPA Valle d'Aosta. A general description of the broadband radiometers can be found elsewhere (e.g., Diémoz et al., 2011). The broadband radiometers operated at the observatory are calibrated once per year with reference to a double-monochromator spectroradiometer (Bentham, DTMc300F), which is in turn calibrated with reference to the world standard QASUME by using a set of 1000 W and 200 W lamps. This ensures physical traceability to the International System of Units (SI) through a well assessed calibration chain.

2.3 Measurement protocol and locations

The data sampling for this study extended over several periods and locations reported in Table 2. They are summarized here below:

1. With the initial objective of testing the accuracy of the electronic dosimeters, the dosimeters were exposed to sunlight over a horizontal surface for almost 24 hours next to the reference instrumentation (period C1 in Table 2). This part was accomplished at the solar and atmospheric observatory of ARPA in Saint-Christophe, Italy (570 m a.s.l, 45° 45' N, 7° 21' E). Saint-Christophe is located on a valley floor in a context of complex orography, with surrounding mountains as high as 4000 m a.s.l. The EUVs were positioned at a distance of about 30 cm from each other so that they would not interfere with each other and they were firmly fixed using plastic clamps (Fig. 2). A slight horizontal misalignment of the dosimeters (towards the west

Figure 2: Physical setup of the EUVs during the calibration/comparison periods C1-C3.

Table 2: Measurement schedule.

Date	Dosimeter(s)	Event
2023/07/10-11	SU01 SU02 SU09	Calibration/comparison with reference instrumentation (C1) – Clear sky (15:15 - 19:00 on 10 July, 5:00 - 15:00 on 11 July)
2023/07/18	SU02	Calibration/comparison with reference instrumentation (C2) – Broken clouds (8:20 to 14:00)
2023/07/18	SU01 SU09	Low-altitude personal dosimetry campaigns (D1)
2023/07/27	SU01	High-altitude personal dosimetry campaign (D2)
2023/07/31	SU01 SU02 SU09	Calibration/comparison with reference instrumentation to test medium-term stability (C3) – Clear sky
2023/08/01	SU09	Comparison with reference instrumentation (C4) – Dosimeter in vertical position)

direction) might have been possible owing to the simple arrangement, however the resulting error is estimated to be much lower than the overall measurement uncertainty. The dosimeters measured the UVI every 20 s, which was averaged over 5 minutes for comparison with the reference radiometer.

The same setup was repeated one week later (C2) and again after the personal dosimetry campaigns (C3), to check the short- and medium-term stability, respectively (results are presented in Sect. 3.3).

2. To collect data representative of the personal exposure, two dosimetry campaigns were organized. Two dosimeters (SU01 and SU09) were worn on the wrist by three volunteers, as this body site is considered a reliable proxy for personal dosimetry of UVR (Thieden et al., 2000).

D1: In the first real-life experiment, the EUVs were given to two individuals aged 16 and 81 and they were employed in Aosta, at the bottom of the valley (about 580 m a.s.l.). The first individual spent the morning studying at home and the afternoon in the garden, but still in a shaded place. The second individual spent the morning

Figure 3: Comparison of dosimeter SU09 with reference instrumentation before the recalibration with the reference radiometer in period C1.

doing outdoor activities, the first part of the afternoon inside his house and the rest of the afternoon running errands (e.g., buying groceries and driving). The activities are representative of conditions of moderate exposure to sunlight.

D2: To assess human exposure in a high altitude environment and test how the dosimeters perform in a high-exposure setting, a dosimeter was given to a subject aged 18 that went on a hike in the mountains. UVR is generally more intense at high altitude due to the lower extinction of UV radiation by the atmospheric species. The subject went on a hike on July, 27th 2023 in Saint-Jacques, Aosta Valley, Italy, at about 1700 m a.s.l. at the lowest point and 2400 m a.s.l. at the highest point. He walked on a relatively shaded path from 9:30 until about 11:30 CEST and then proceeded in an open area where he was exposed to direct sunlight for about 5 hours.

3. A final experiment (C4) was conducted again at the observatory to assess the ratio between the exposure in the vertical orientation (dosimeter) and the exposure in the horizontal orientation (radiometer).

3. Results

3.1 Assessment of the calibration by the manufacturer

Figure 3 depicts the comparison between the UV Index obtained during period C1 with the original calibration from the manufacturer by one of the dosimeters (SU09, taken as an

Figure 4: Period C1, comparison of the dosimeter performance using single-factor calibration and two-factor calibration.

example) and the reference broadband UV radiometer. While the daily evolution, with a maximum corresponding to the solar noon, is well captured by both devices, these results show an overestimation by the dosimeter (of about 10%), notably in the central hours of the day. At the same time, the dosimeter estimates during the morning and the afternoon, at medium UV Indices, are more accurate. Dependencies on the solar zenith angle are quite typical of simple UV instruments, and can arise due to either inaccurate spectral response (not perfectly matching the erythemal action spectrum) or angular response (not perfectly corresponding to the cosine of the solar zenith angle). The observed overestimation at noon could be explained assuming that the dosimeters were calibrated by the manufacturer at larger solar zenith angles compared to those reached during C1. Comparable results were also obtained with the other two dosimeters, with some differences both in terms of raw counts and UVI (not shown).

3.2 Recalibration using reference radiometers

In order to better fit the reference data with the dosimeters, and to also homogenize the UVI data from the three dosimeters with each other, a new calibration was calculated from the data collected in C1. To do so, several techniques were tested:

1. A least squares linear regression (with two factors) (in the form $y = ax + b$, hereafter referred to as two-factor calibration, same as used by the manufacturer) between the counts from each dosimeter (y) and the UVI from the broadband radiometer (x) was

performed. The most uncertain dataset (dosimeters) was chosen as the y variable in order to avoid regression dilution (e.g., Hutcheon et al., 2010). The resulting function was then reversed to obtain calibrated UVIs. Unfortunately, after the calibration, the results presented non-physical, non-zero UVI values during the night, owing to the presence of a regression offset (b).

2. To counteract this effect, a second calibration with no offset (in the form $y = ax$, hereafter referred to as single-factor calibration) was attempted. Indeed, we did not observe any relevant dark signal by the dosimeters during the night. This parametrization provided more physical results at night. The calibrated dosimeter data resulting from this second fit are presented in Fig. 4. This shows that for UVIs higher than two, the results with the single-factor calibration match the ones with the two-factor calibration. For lower UVIs, the two-factor calibration approximates more closely the radiometer. For UVIs approaching zero, the calibration with no offset is more accurate, as it actually provides values close to zero.

3.3 Stability tests

On 18 July, a new comparison (C2) with the reference radiometer was conducted to assess the short-term stability of the dosimeters. First, the UVI data collected by the radiometer during C1 and C2 periods were compared (Fig. 5). Interestingly, on that day, the atmospheric conditions were not the same as in the previous test, hence the data can also be used to determine how the dosimeters work in a different scenario. Indeed, sparse clouds were present in the sky. Moreover, the total ozone column concentration from a co-located Brewer spectrophotometer was lower in C2 compared to C1 (290 DU on average, instead of 310 DU), potentially leading to an increase in UVR. However, at the same time, a strong episode of Saharan dust advection occurred, as revealed by two co-located sun photometers, thus counterbalancing the effect of ozone on UVR. Despite these differences, the higher envelope of the UVIs measured in C2 by the reference radiometer (i.e., the data least affected by clouds) were very similar to the ones obtained in C1 (Fig. 5). Sudden drops in the UVI are visible when clouds block the direct sunlight.

A new calibration fit was obtained by applying the single-factor calibration approach using data collected in C2. As shown in Fig. 6 (for SU09 dosimeter as an example), the UVI values determined with the single-factor calibration in C1 (green) and in C2 (blue) are very similar with each other and very close to the radiometer. The residual differences might depend merely on the smaller sample of data used to calculate the second calibration fit or perhaps on unscreened clouds that might have led to a less accurate line of best fit. Indeed, the data were screened using a very simple standard deviation criteria. The use of co-located instruments such as a cloudcam and a sunphotometer, and manual quality controls could allow better screening, resulting in a more accurate calibration fit.

Figure 5: Comparison between the UVI measured by the reference radiometer during C1 (black) and C2 (red).

Figure 6: C2 period, comparison of the dosimeter performance using different single-factor calibrations.

Figure 7: C3 period, comparison of the dosimeter performance using single-factor calibration obtained in C3 (blue), in C1 (orange) and with the calibration from the manufacturer.

A final stability test (C3) was performed after the personal dosimetry campaigns. Unfortunately, the dosimeters showed a large change in their internal calibration relative to the first tests (C1 and C2). The UVI from each dosimeter obtained with the calibration from C1 differed a lot (-15.8% for SU09 and -42.6% for SU01) from the reference standard, as shown for SU01 in Fig. 7. The reason for the inconsistency in measurements over a span of about three weeks is not clear. The dosimeters might have undergone mechanical shock while being used, however we cannot identify any clear discontinuity in the datasets and the decrease is similar in both dosimeters. It should be noted that the reference radiometer is continuously compared to a double monochromator Bentham spectroradiometer, and did not show any relevant calibration change in this period. Other instrumental factors may have influenced the stability of the dosimeters, such as degradation/aging of some components or the charge of the internal battery (which had been fully charged some months before, but left unused for about 5 months), and they will be discussed with the manufacturer. As the exact moment of the calibration change is not known and the degradation could have been gradual, the average of the two calibrations (C1 and C3) was calculated and employed to process the raw data collected during the dosimetry campaigns. The contribution to the overall uncertainty originating from this assumption will be considered in the final results.

In addition to the observed instabilities, it is reported that dosimeter SU02 completely shut down after real-life usage and no longer gave any output. The device was still recognized by the operating software, yet it did not record any data. Even after repeating the test multiple times, SU02 never returned any output.

Figure 8: Comparison of UVI recorded by SU09 (blue) with reference instrumentation during D1.

Figure 9: Comparison between the reference radiometer at Saint-Christophe (red) and the dosimeter employed in D2 at high altitude (using single-factor calibration in C1 period before the field campaign, green, and in C3 period after the field campaign, blue).

3.4 Results from the personal dosimetry campaigns

3.4.1 UVR exposure in day-to-day life at low altitude

The average erythemally weighted radiant exposure during D1 was $65 \pm 10 \text{ J}_{\text{ery}} \text{ m}^{-2}$ for both of the individuals. The large uncertainty is related to the observed and unexplained changes of calibration between C1/C2 and C3. Compared to the available environmental solar irradiance recorded by the radiometer on the same day, the dosimeter data were generally much lower (as shown in Fig. 8), mainly because the two subjects spent most of their day in shaded places and were exposed to high UVIs only occasionally. However, even during the short periods of highest exposure, the UVI never reached the UVI values recorded by the radiometer, likely due to the orientation of the dosimeter.

From this, we can infer that during a day with regular exposure, the dose is far from the MED. On the other hand, what might occur in case of such low dose levels is the insurgence of vitamin D deficiency.

3.4.2 UVR exposure at high altitude

The device worn by the volunteer (SU01) during D2 did not register the inverse bell-shaped curve typical of the daily cycle of solar irradiance on a horizontal surface (Fig. 9). Even when the subject was in the open fields, only some spikes as large as 3.5 UVI were detected whenever the dosimeter was exposed to the direct sunlight. These peak values are much lower than the maximum UVI measured on the same day by the broadband radiometer at Saint-Christophe, situated about 1300 m lower down on the valley floor. Since the UVI is generally larger at higher altitudes suggests that the actual UVI in Saint-Jacques might have been even higher than in Saint-Christophe. The main reason for the observed differences between the EUV measurements and expected UVI on a horizontal surface could be the fact that the dosimeter is rarely aligned to the sun for the whole sampling time (20 s). For this reason, some tests were performed at the observatory with the dosimeter placed in a vertical orientation (C4, discussed in Sect. 3.5). Moreover, uncertainties discussed in Sect. 3.3 must be taken into account.

Despite the generally low UVIs registered by the dosimeter, the dose calculated by integrating these data over time and multiplying the result by 0.025 W m^{-2} corresponds to $242 \text{ J}_{\text{ery}} \text{ m}^{-2}$, which closely approximate the MED for the skin type (II) of the volunteer (250 J m^{-2}). Indeed, the subject reported mild erythema after exposure. The protective effect of the sunscreen, which had presumably low SPF and was applied only once in the morning, could have vanished due to sweating while hiking.

3.5 Difference in exposure recorded with horizontal and vertical EUV settings

A new still-exposure test was performed at the observatory during C4 to assess the ratio between the exposure in a vertical orientation and that in a horizontal orientation. This test takes advantage of the flexibility of the dosimeters, which can be installed in any setting.

Indeed, dosimeter SU09 was again placed on a rail (as in C1-C3), but vertically instead of

Figure 10: Period C4, comparison of the dosimeter performance using single-factor calibration in C1.

horizontally. The EUV sensor roughly faced south (i.e. the azimuth direction corresponding to minimum air mass factor, at noon) and recorded from 9:10 a.m. until 1:53 p.m. (solar time).

The UVI data collected in the vertical setting, processed with the single-factor calibration in C1 as addressed in Sect. 3.3, were significantly lower than the reference radiometer (Fig. 10). The reason is that, in this vertical setting, the incidence angle is large, since it is complementary to the solar zenith angle, which is low at noon, especially in summer.

An approximate “conversion factor” of about 2.7 between the two observation geometries was calculated, showing that the vertical dosimeter (even in the most favorable azimuthal orientation, i.e. to the south) was exposed to about one third of the energy received by a horizontal surface. This ratio actually varies according to the position of the sun, since the shape of the solar spectra incident on the two surfaces do not necessarily coincide and the dosimeter was not perfectly directed to the south.

4 Discussion

The main issue encountered during the use of the EUV dosimeters was their instability. Based on the data collected in this study, it is hard to tell if there were any signs of degradation from the beginning of the tests, since no previous measurements were available. The measurements in C1 span less than 24 hours and they include only one

afternoon and the following morning, thus making it difficult to assess the stability of the instrument, especially considering the large overestimation during the central hours. Moreover, the dosimeters were not installed with a perfectly horizontal leveling, because of technical constraints (the dosimeters have a plastic, rectangular ring under them to fix them to wrist bands and this structure made it impossible to keep them completely horizontal). This misalignment could have partially masked the evidence of a slight degradation during C1. However, as no degradation was expected, the tilt angle was not measured, which makes it difficult to calculate the impact of the horizontal misalignment.

In a future study, the dosimeters should be exposed to the sunlight for a longer period, side by side with the reference instrumentation. This test could be very useful to check if the degradation has to do with the mechanical stress - e.g. due to the use at high altitude, intense movement - or something else related to the ambient use.

It should be noticed that SU02 was the dosimeter that received the largest UVI dose during the testing. This could suggest a correlation between exposure and degradation, but these are only speculations and further investigations are needed to confirm the hypothesis.

5 Conclusions

This study represents the first effort in Italy to test the EUV dosimeters. These are very promising devices, their ease of use and accurate measurements (at least, in the calibration phase) being the main assets. Three experiments, with the aim of comparing and calibrating the dosimeters with respect to reference instrumentation, were organized in the course of the study. Data collected during the first two exercises (C1-C2) showed excellent stability and agreement with the reference radiometer, demonstrating the possibility of providing the UV Index within 10% accuracy (with respect to the reference instrument) and 10% precision (among the dosimeters). However, the third exercise (C3), performed after the on-field dosimetry campaigns, revealed that medium-term severe instabilities in the EUVs may occur, suggesting the need of regularly comparing the dosimeters with reference instruments.

Despite these issues, the results obtained by three volunteers in two personal dosimetry campaigns (D1-D2) at different altitudes were consistent with the expected exposure patterns. While individuals wearing the device during day-to-day life at low altitude received very low UV doses even in summer, the volunteer hiking at high altitude was exposed to the strong UVR typical of the Alpine environment in summer and to the consequent risk of sunburn, even after the application of a low-SPF UV sunscreen.

The results from this experiment should be taken into account when drafting sun safety guidelines at mountainous sites and can serve as a basis for future exercises involving a larger number of volunteers.

Author contributions

This work was carried out in the frame of Leonardo Di Tommaso's high school internship at ARPA Valle d'Aosta in summer 2023. LDT conceptualized the study, organized the campaign, performed the measurements and

analyzed the data. AB, HD and AMS contributed to the interpretation of the results. All authors carefully reviewed and contributed to the final manuscript.

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